

25 **Abstract**

26 Notwithstanding lactate-driven dark fermentation (LD-DF) can cope with inhibition
27 issues associated with the over-proliferation of lactate producers, there is still a
28 knowledge gap about the role of key operational parameters. In this study, the effect of
29 pH and total solids (TS) content on the co-production of hydrogen and carboxylic acids,
30 including medium-chain carboxylic acids (MCCAs), from food waste (FW) via LD-DF
31 was investigated. A series of batch fermentations was conducted at 5.5, 6.0, 6.5, and no
32 pH control, while maintaining constant the TS content at 5%. The higher the operational
33 pH, the lower the accumulation of lactate and the higher the extent and rate of hydrogen
34 production, sustaining a maximum hydrogen production yield and rate of 81 NmL/g VS
35 fed and 9 NL/L-d, respectively, at pH 6.5. In a second series of batch tests, the TS
36 content was adjusted to 5, 7.5 and 10% while pH was set at 6.5. The highest hydrogen
37 production performance (103 NmL/g-VS fed and 13.3 NL/L-d) was achieved at 7.5%
38 TS, which also resulted in the highest accumulation of MCCAs, particularly of caproate,
39 with an associated titer of 8.7 g/L. Hydrogen production plateaued with the exhaustion
40 of lactate regardless of the condition tested. Overall, the results obtained confirmed the
41 key role of pH and TS content in the LD-DF of FW and suggested that this non-
42 conventional route may be an alternative approach to cope with lactate flux diverted
43 toward undesirable non-hydrogen-producing metabolic pathways.

44

45 **Keywords:**

46 Biogás, Biomass valorization, Caproate, Food waste, Hydrogen, Methane.

47 **1. Introduction**

48 The exponential production and accumulation of food waste (FW) has become one of
49 the main challenges to overcome worldwide. The Food and Agriculture Organization
50 (FAO) estimates that nearly a third part of the food produced globally ends up
51 becoming FW along the food consuming chain causing not only economic losses but
52 also social and environmental damage [1]. Most FW ends up on landfills and ultimately
53 generates gaseous (CH_4 , CO_2 , NH_3) and liquid (leachate) emissions. Other management
54 options like composting, anaerobic digestion and thermal conversion represent a much
55 lower percentage of the FW treatments worldwide, mostly due to a reduced scalable
56 capacity, even though FW contains high energy available [2], [3]. In Europe, approx. 88
57 Mt of FW are produced annually, with an associated emission of 186 Mt/year of carbon
58 dioxide (CO_2), 1.7 Mt/year of sulphur dioxide and 0.7 Mt/year of phosphates [4], being
59 equivalent to 15% of all environmental damage caused by the food supply chain in
60 Europe [1].

61 FW is a suitable feedstock for the production of different high-value products
62 via fermentation owing to its high energy content and carbon density [5], [6], [7].
63 Among these bioproducts, hydrogen has gained a tremendous attention as a clean
64 energy substitute of fossil-based fuels because of its high energy density (2.7 times
65 higher than natural gas) combined with the fact that it does not generate CO_2 when is
66 combusted (only water steam) [8], [9]. There is a diverse group of biotechnologies able
67 to produce hydrogen (e.g., dark fermentation (DF), photofermentation, biophotolysis,
68 microbial electrolysis cells). Among them, the DF process has shown relatively superior
69 hydrogen production yields and rates, and flexibility, to manage different types of
70 organic wastes and wastewaters [10]. Furthermore, DF allows for the valorization of

71 FW not only through the production of renewable hydrogen but also of carboxylic acids
72 that can be further used to produce other high added value products. In this context, the
73 production of medium-chain carboxylic acids (MCCAs) opens new routes for FW
74 valorization into green chemicals. Indeed, caproate or heptanoate can be employed for
75 the production of antimicrobial agents, food additives, pharmaceuticals, fragrances, as
76 well as diesel and aviation fuels [15]. The acidogenic effluent of DF, rich in organic
77 acids, can be also fermented by methanogenic bacteria to produce biogas [15], [16].

78 However, despite the numerous efforts made in the DF field over the last two
79 decades, the DF of FW is still challenging, deserving more research to make the process
80 more stable and efficient in terms of hydrogen yield and productivity. Evidence in the
81 literature has shown that the impairment in hydrogen efficiency is mostly caused by the
82 over-growth of lactic acid bacteria (LAB), which are naturally and ubiquitously present
83 in FW and therefore can thrive and proliferate during its storage, transport and disposal
84 chain [10]. The negative effect of LAB in the DF process has been ascribed to the
85 competition with hydrogen-producing bacteria (HPB) for substrate, the acidification of
86 the culture broth due to the production and accumulation of lactate, and the excretion of
87 antimicrobial/inhibitory compounds to the culture broth [10]. In this context,
88 sterilization of the substrate has been proposed to prevent LAB proliferation during DF,
89 making the process more expensive and complex, although this strategy has shown little
90 success since LAB end up thriving again under long-term operation [10], [11].
91 Recently, it has been proposed to tailor the DF towards lactate-utilizing, hydrogen-
92 producing pathways to cope with the presence of LAB [10]. The lactate-driven DF (LD-
93 DF) approach allows harnessing the syntrophic interactions between LAB and HPB that
94 may take place under certain conditions to produce fermentative hydrogen from lactate

95 rather than directly from carbohydrates [12], [13], [14]. Besides making the process
96 more cost-effective and less complex, the LD-DF may bring about some desirable
97 bioactivities such as pH regulation (due to the production and consumption of lactate),
98 substrate hydrolysis, biomass retention, oxygen depletion and substrate detoxification
99 [10]. Despite these latent process advantages, studies are lacking to support LD-DF as a
100 viable option for the production of hydrogen. Furthermore, although the impact of some
101 key process parameters such as pH and total solids (TS) content on the DF process
102 performance have been extensively studied [17], there is still limited knowledge about
103 their effect on the LD-DF process of FW.

104 This study aimed at evaluating the production of renewable hydrogen with the
105 concomitant formation of organic acids, including MCCAs, from FW through the LD-
106 DF process. Emphasis was paid on investigating the effect of operational pH and TS
107 content on the hydrogen production yield and the maximum volumetric hydrogen
108 production rate, and on the titer and distribution of organic acids involved. The
109 methanogenic potential of the acidogenic effluent obtained at optimum operational
110 conditions was further evaluated using conventional biochemical methane potential
111 (BMP) tests.

112

113 **2. Materials and methods**

114 2.1 Inocula and feedstock

115 The acidogenic inoculum source was digestate obtained from a pilot-scale anaerobic
116 digester treating FW under mesophilic conditions. Heat-shock pretreatment (90 °C for
117 20 min) was used to kill methanogens. Three cycles of subculturing were carried out
118 using the pre-treated microbial culture as the inoculum and lactose as the carbon source,

119 according to García-Depraect et al. (2022) [18]. The resulting enriched mixed culture
120 was thus used as the inoculum, which has been previously characterised to be composed
121 of the genera *Lactobacillus* (55%), *Klebsiella* (28%), *Clostridium* (11%),
122 *Stenotrophomonas* (3%), *Acinetobacter* (1.8%), among others [18]. Similarly, a fresh
123 inoculum for the BMP tests was obtained from the mesophilic anaerobic digester of the
124 Valladolid (Spain) wastewater treatment plant. The methanogenic inoculum was
125 preincubated at 37 °C under anaerobic conditions for 7 days before inoculation. The
126 preincubated anaerobic sludge exhibited a pH of 7.5 and a TS and volatile solids (VS)
127 content of 15.8 and 8.63 g/L, respectively.

128 Simulated FW was used as a model substrate following the recipe reported by
129 Neves et al. (2008) [19] to mimic restaurant FW. This FW was based on a grinded
130 mixture of potato flakes (78%), chicken breast (14%), white cabbage (4%) and pork lard
131 (4% w/w), as a source of carbohydrates, proteins, and lipids, respectively. A 17.5-kg
132 batch of FW was prepared and stored in several plastic bags at -20 °C until use. The pH
133 of the FW was 6.2 ± 0.05 , while its COD and TS concentration accounted for 295 g
134 O₂/kg and 211 g TS/kg, respectively. The composition of the FW (% w/w on a dry
135 basis) was as follows: carbohydrates (50.7 ± 3.8), proteins (25.4 ± 0.3), lipids (20.03)
136 and ash (4.7). Such proportions were well associated with an ultimate analysis based on
137 carbon (C; $50.3 \pm 0.7\%$), hydrogen (H, $7.3 \pm 0.3\%$), oxygen (O, $33.6 \pm 0.2\%$), nitrogen
138 (N, $4.1 \pm 0.1\%$) and phosphorus (P, 0.3%). No sulphur (S) was detected.

139 2.2 Experimental set-up and evaluation of operational conditions for hydrogen

140 production

141 Batch experiments were performed in two identical 1-L glass stirred tank reactors with a
142 working volume of 0.8 L. The LD-DF of FW was carried out at 37 °C under magnetic

143 stirring at \approx 200 rpm. The fermentations were conducted with a cultivation broth
144 initially composed of 720 mL synthetic FW (previously grinded for 3 minutes using a
145 conventional kitchen blender), and inoculum at 10% (v/v) with a volatile suspended
146 solids (VSS) concentration of 0.32 ± 0.03 g/L. The hydrogenogenic inoculum was
147 preincubated overnight at 37 °C using lactose as the sole carbon source at a
148 concentration of 10 g/L in 2.1 L gas-tight glass flasks with 0.9 L of mineral salt medium
149 (the pre-inoculum size was 10% v/v). The composition of the growth medium was (in
150 g/L) as follows: NH₄Cl, 2.4; K₂HPO₄, 2.4; MgCl₂, 1.18; KH₂PO₄, 0.6; CaCl₂, 0.11; and
151 FeCl₂, 0.024.

152 In a first series of batch tests, the TS content was fixed at 5% and the influence
153 of pH on the LD-DF of FW was investigated by automatically controlling it at 5.5, 6.0,
154 and 6.5. Additionally, a fermentation was also performed without pH control (initial pH
155 of 5.9). In a second series of batch tests, the influence of TS concentration was
156 investigated by adjusting the TS content at 5, 7.5 and 10%, while maintaining constant
157 the optimum pH previously determined (i.e., 6.5). TS content was adjusted using tap
158 water. All experiments were conducted in duplicate. The pH of the fermentation was
159 automatically controlled by adding NaOH 3M or HCl 3M with a pH controller (BSV,
160 EVOPH-P-5 model, Spain). Gas production and composition, pH, organic acids, and the
161 cumulative volume of NaOH/HCl were periodically measured. The performance of the
162 process was measured based on the rates and yields of hydrogen production, VS
163 removal efficiency and organic acids profile.

164 2.3 Biochemical methane potential tests

165 The BMP of the acidogenic broth collected from the fermentations performed at the
166 optimal pH (i.e., 6.5) and TS content (i.e., 7.5%) was evaluated in order to elucidate the

167 potential enhancement in the methane yield and kinetics supported by the LD-DF
168 process. The substrates tested were the acidogenic broths collected after 24 and 48 h of
169 fermentation time. These sampling points were chosen based on the cultivation times at
170 which the production of hydrogen (24 h) and organic acids (48 h) peaked. Additionally,
171 non-fermented FW was also evaluated to simulate a one-stage anaerobic digestion
172 process. The BMP assays were performed in 2.1 L gas-tight glass flasks with 0.5 L of
173 working volume, at a constant temperature (37 °C) and agitation rate (4.5 rpm) using a
174 roller shaker (Wheaton Scientific Products, USA). The BMP tests were conducted at a
175 fixed substrate to inoculum ratio of 0.25 (on a VS basis), supplemented with 5 g/L of
176 NaHCO₃ as buffering agent to prevent acidification of the medium, and flushed with
177 helium for 5 min to remove residual oxygen from the headspace. Blanks containing
178 only inoculum with 5 g/L NaHCO₃ were set to quantify the endogenous biogas
179 production, while microcrystalline cellulose (Merck Ltd., Germany, CAS number 9004–
180 34-6) was used as the positive control, as recommended by Holliger et al. (2016) [20].
181 All BMP tests were carried out in triplicate. BMP was estimated using the manometric
182 method, recording and releasing the overpressure in the headspace to achieve
183 atmospheric pressure before each biogas measurement. The headspace pressure and the
184 composition (CO₂ and CH₄) of biogas were periodically measured, avoiding
185 overpressure on the gas-tight reactors (> 200 mbars). The final pH of the broth and
186 organic acids concentrations were also measured at the end of the experiment.

187

188 2.4 Analytical methods

189 Gas composition (i.e., H₂, CO₂ and CH₄) was measured by gas chromatography using a
190 Varian CP-3800 gas chromatograph (GC) coupled with a thermal conductivity detector

191 (TCD) and equipped with a Varian CP-Molsieve 5A capillary column (15 m × 0.53 mm
192 × 15 μm) interconnected with a Varian CP-PoreBOND Q capillary column (25 m ×
193 0.53 mm × 10 μm), using helium as the carrier gas, according to Alcántara et al. (2015)
194 [21]. Organic acids (i.e., lactic acid, acetic acid, formic acid, propionic acid, butyric
195 acid, isobutyric acid, valeric acid, isovaleric acid, caproic acid, isocaproic acid, and
196 heptanoic acid) were measured by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)
197 using a Alliance HPLC system (model e2695, USA) equipped with an ultraviolet (UV)
198 detector (214 nm) and an Aminex chromatographic column kept at 75 °C (HPX-87H,
199 Bio Rad, USA), preceded by a Micro-Guard Cation H⁺ refill cartridge of 30 × 4.6 mm
200 (Bio Rad, USA) as a pre-column. Sulfuric acid 25 mM was used as the eluent at a flow
201 rate of 0.7 mL/min. Due to their expected low titers at the end of the BMP assays,
202 organic acids were quantified by gas chromatography using a Agilent GC (7820A,
203 Agilent, USA) equipped with a flame ionization detector (FID) and a packed column
204 (10% SP-1000 + 1% H₃PO₄ on Chromosorb[®] W acid washed 100/120 mesh size, 2 m ×
205 3.175 mm; Teknokroma, Spain). The temperatures of the injection port and detector
206 were kept both at 350 °C. The oven temperature was initially maintained at 135 °C for
207 10 min, then it was increased to 151 °C at a rate of 3 °C/min, and finally ramped at 8
208 °C/min to 180 °C and held for 5 min. Nitrogen, at a flow rate of 45 mL/min, was
209 employed as the carrier gas. The flow rate of hydrogen and air was 45 and 350 mL/min,
210 respectively [18]. Carbohydrates were measured using the phenol-sulphuric acid method
211 based on the digestion of 1 mL of sample with 0.6 mL of phenol at 5% v/v and 3.6 mL
212 of sulphuric acid at 95% v/v. Concentration was determined by the absorbance method
213 using an Spectro Star Nano from BMG LACTECH. Protein content was measured using
214 the total nitrogen concentration by the Kjeldahl method [22], with a nitrogen-to-protein

215 index of 6.25 [18]. Lipid content was analysed using the gravimetric method performed
216 by the Regional Service for Agri-food Research and Development (SERIDA, Spain).
217 The elemental composition of FW (C, H, O, N and S) was analysed using an elemental
218 analyzer EA FLASH 2000 (Thermo Fisher Scientific) coupled with a TCD detector and
219 a Mettler Toledo XP6 microscale, using helium as a carrier (140 mL/min) and reference
220 (100 ml/min) gas coupled with oxygen (250 ml/min) at 900 °C furnace temperature for
221 C, H, N, and S measurements; and helium as carrier (130 mL/min) and reference (100
222 mL/min) gas at 1060 °C furnace temperature for O measurement; based on the internal
223 procedure of the Central Instrumental Laboratories of the University of Burgos (Spain).
224 Finally, P content was determined by inductively coupled plasma optical emission
225 spectroscopy (ICP-OES) based on the internal procedure of the Laboratory of
226 Instrumental Techniques at the University of Valladolid (Spain).

227 2.5 Data treatment

228 Data on the cumulative hydrogen and methane production were further processed using
229 the modified Gompertz kinetic model, according to Eq. 1, where H_{max} is the maximum
230 cumulative hydrogen or methane production (NmL), R_{max} is the maximum production
231 rate of hydrogen or methane (NmL/h and NmL/d for hydrogen and methane,
232 respectively), λ is the duration of *lag* phase (t), and t is the incubation time (in hours and
233 days for hydrogen and methane production, respectively).

$$234 \quad H = H_{max} * \exp \left\{ -\exp \left[\frac{R_{max} * e}{H_{max}} * (\lambda - t) + 1 \right] \right\} \quad (1)$$

235 The methane yield from the BMP assays was analysed according to Eq. 2 [23], where
236 BMP is the volume of methane produced per gram of VS added (NmL CH₄/g VS
237 added), V_S is the mean value of the accumulated volume of methane produced from the

238 substrate (NmL), V_B is the mean value of the accumulated volume of methane derived
 239 from the control blank (NmL), m_{IS} and m_{IB} stands for the total amount of inoculum (g
 240 VS) in the substrate and blank, respectively, and m_{VS} is the total amount of substrate (g
 241 VS).

$$242 \text{ BMP} = \left[V_S - \left(V_B \frac{m_{IS}}{m_{IB}} \right) \right] / m_{VS} \quad (2)$$

243 The theoretical maximum methane production of the model substrate was calculated
 244 based on Eq. 3 [24], where: Y_c , Y_p and Y_l are the methane yields of carbohydrates (0.395
 245 NmL CH₄/g), proteins (0.5 NmL CH₄/g) and lipids (0.854 NmL CH₄/g), respectively.
 246 W_c , W_p , and W_l stand for the empirical content of carbohydrate, proteins and lipids in the
 247 model substrate, respectively [24].

$$248 Y \left(\frac{m^3 \text{CH}_4}{\text{Kg}} \right) = Y_c * W_c + Y_p * W_p + Y_l * W_l \quad (3)$$

249 The acetate produced by homoacetogenesis ($A_{\text{Chomoacet}}$) was estimated based on Eq. 4
 250 [25], where [Ac], [But], [Prop] and [H₂] are the concentrations (in mmol) of acetate,
 251 butyrate, propionate and hydrogen, respectively.

$$252 A_{\text{Chomoacet}} = (2[\text{Ac}] + 2[\text{But}] - [\text{Prop}] - [\text{H}_2]) / 6 \quad (4)$$

253 Bioconversion ratios (BR) were calculated as a measure of the degree of acidification,
 254 according to Eq. 5, where COD eq and C eq is the sum of COD and carbon equivalent
 255 concentrations (in g/L), respectively, of all the organic acids measured at the end of the
 256 process, and TCOD_{FW} and TC_{FW} is the total COD and carbon content (in g /L) of the
 257 FW, respectively. COD equivalence for organic acids was determined according to Eqs.
 258 6 and 7, where OA is the molecular formula of a given organic acid, and a , b , c and d
 259 are the number of moles of OA, O₂, H₂O and CO₂ based on the analysis of
 260 stoichiometry for complete combustion.

261
$$BR (\%) = \frac{COD_{eq} \text{ (or C eq)}}{TCOD_{FW} \text{ (or } TC_{FW})} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

262
$$aOA + bO_2 = cH_2O + dCO_2 \quad (6)$$

263
$$COD_{equiv.} = \frac{aO_2}{bOA} \quad (7)$$

264

265 **3. Results and discussion**

266 3.1 Influence of pH and TS concentration on the lactate-based fermentative hydrogen 267 production

268 At a fixed TS of 5%, the highest hydrogen yield (80.9 NmL/g VS fed) was achieved at a
269 pH of 6.5, which was 46 and 9.6% higher than that recorded at a constant pH of 5.5 and
270 6.0, respectively (Table 1). As expected, it was found that the modified Gompertz
271 kinetic model (Eq. 1) adequately described the cumulative hydrogen production
272 experimentally recorded, with coefficients of determination above 0.99 regardless of the
273 pH and TS concentration tested (Fig. 1, Table 1). Based on the estimated parameters,
274 the maximum hydrogen production potential (*Hmax*) achieved in the assays conducted
275 at a fixed TS concentration of 5% and a pH of 5.5, 6.0 and 6.5 accounted for 2.7, 3.6
276 and 3.9 NL/L of reactor, respectively, with corresponding maximum volumetric
277 hydrogen production rates (*Rmax*) of 67.4, 204.4 and 373.9 NmL/L-h. Remarkably, no
278 hydrogen was produced in the assay conducted without pH control due to the rapid
279 acidification of the cultivation broth, which reached a pH < 5 in less than 2 h of
280 fermentation. A relatively high VS removal was observed at the end of the
281 fermentations, with removal efficiencies of 48.0, 53.8 and 52.7% at pH 5.5, 6.0 and 6.5,
282 respectively. No methanogenic activity was observed during the test period for all
283 conditions tested. This test series confirmed the key role of pH in governing the

284 efficiency of the LD-DF of FW in terms of hydrogen production yield and rate. The
285 results obtained showed a clear improvement in hydrogen production performance when
286 approaching neutral pH values.

287 The operational pH is one of the key operational factors in the DF process
288 because it greatly affects not only the microbial structure but also the metabolism in
289 relation to the metabolic fluxes, biocatalytic activity (including hydrogen-producing
290 enzymes), biomass growth and substrate degradation [10], [17], [26]. Previous studies
291 showed that hydrogen production via LD-DF is heavily impacted by pH, occurring at
292 pH values between 3.8 and 7.5, but mostly in the pH range of 5–7, and obtaining
293 superior performances at pH values of 5.5–6.5 [10]. It has been argued that a suitable
294 balance between the production of lactate by LAB and its further consumption by HPB
295 is required in the LD-DF, and that pH affects such microbial equilibrium [10], [13]. It
296 was thus hypothesized that a fixed pH of 5.5 somehow affected the balance between
297 HPB and LAB, been more conducive to the growth of LAB as endorsed by the higher
298 accumulation of lactate recorded (see section 3.2). Contrarily, a near-neutral pH might
299 ensure balance and syntrophy between LAB and lactate-utilizing HPB, allowing them to
300 co-exist, thus leading to lower lactate accumulation and higher hydrogen production.
301 Further molecular analyses are obviously required to prove this hypothesis.

302 Nonetheless, it seems a plausible assumption that can explain the clear trends observed:
303 the higher the culture pH, the lower the accumulation of lactate and the higher the extent
304 and rate of hydrogen production.

305 The optimal pH found for hydrogen production of 6.5 was thus set as operational
306 pH in the test series assessing the influence of TS content on the process. It was found
307 that a TS content of 7.5% supported the highest hydrogen yield (103.4 NmL/g VS fed),

308 which was $\approx 29\%$ higher than that exhibited at 5 and 10% TS concentrations. The
309 maximum cumulative hydrogen production recorded at 5, 7.5 and 10% TS was 3.8, 7.4
310 and 7.6 NL/L of reactor, respectively, with corresponding R_{max} values of 373.9, 556.1
311 and 603.7 NmL/L-h, respectively (Table 1), and associated VS removal efficiencies of
312 52.5, 55.4 and 59.8%, respectively. The increase in hydrogen productivities observed
313 when the TS concentration (which is positively correlated with substrate concentration)
314 was increased from 5 to 7.5% could be explained by the preference of the microbiota
315 towards lactate-utilizing, hydrogen-producing pathways at higher FW concentration.
316 Wu et al. (2012) [27] observed that a higher substrate concentration could enhance the
317 hydrogen production using lactate and acetate as substrates because electron equivalents
318 required for biomass growth are rapidly satisfied, leaving an excess of electron
319 equivalents for hydrogen production. However, the apparent viscosity of the cultivation
320 medium at 10% TS was too high and led to an inefficient magnetic stirring, which in
321 turn impaired the contact between substrate and biocatalyst and therefore negatively
322 affected the FW-to-hydrogen bioconversion. Previous studies have reported a severe
323 decrease in hydrogen yield at high TS concentrations, especially when surpassing the
324 15% TS content (dry DF) due to an increase of lactate production in opposition to
325 hydrogen production [28], [29]. It is well known that a suitable balance between
326 hydrolytic and fermentative bioactivities is a prerequisite for efficient hydrogen
327 production, especially using complex particulate substrates [30], [31]. In this context, it
328 has been previously hypothesized that the presence of particulate material may alter the
329 balance between LAB and HPB in the LD-DF, leading to higher LAB activities at
330 higher TS content, while lower TS contents may boost the activity of HPB [32].
331 Although the maximum TS content herein tested remained below 15%, the

332 accumulation of lactate at 10% TS was comparatively higher than that at 5 and 7.5% (as
333 will be discussed in section 3.2), which might also explain the decrease in hydrogen
334 yield when augmenting the TS from 7.5 to 10%.

335 The extent of *lag* phase is other parameter highly influenced by the culture pH.
336 The shortest *lag* phase (based on the modified Gompertz model parameter λ) of 4.5 h
337 was recorded at pH 6.0, followed by the 6.3 h determined at a pH of 6.5 regardless of
338 the TS content. A longer *lag* phase, on average, of 7.3 h was observed at a pH of 5.5.
339 Thus, the *lag* phase at pH 6.0 was 38.5 and 62% shorter than those at pH 6.5 and 5.5,
340 respectively. It is worth highlighting that the higher *lag* phase recorded for pH 5.5
341 reinforces the hypothesis based on the balanced growth between LAB and HPB outlined
342 above. In this context, Dareioti et al. (2014) [33] observed shorter *lag* phases at
343 increasing pH values during the LD-DF of an organic mix containing (in volume) 55%
344 olive mill wastewater, 40% cheese whey and 5% liquid cow manure by a mixed
345 acidogenic culture under mesophilic conditions. In that study, the shortest *lag* phase of
346 26.1 h was recorded at a pH of 6.5, which was 3.5 times shorter than that at pH 5.5.
347 Similarly, García-Depraect et al. (2019a) [13] evaluated the influence of pH on the
348 mesophilic LD-DF of tequila vinasses by a mixed culture and found that the duration of
349 the *lag* phase was shortened from 111 at a constant pH of 5.5 to 28.5 h at a pH of 6.5.
350 Indeed, the duration of the hydrogen production phase increased at decreasing pH
351 values. The end of the hydrogen production phase in this study was estimated as the
352 process time where 95% of the total hydrogen production was reached (t_{95}). Hence, the
353 shortest t_{95} occurred at a pH of 6.5, where 23.9 ± 2.1 h of fermentation were recorded at
354 the three TS contents tested. Such t_{95} was 20.8 and 161.6% shorter than the assays
355 performed at pH 6.0 and pH 5.5, respectively.

356 The hydrogen yields and rates available in the literature vary significantly
357 depending on several factors such as the type of operational conditions, feedstock and
358 inoculum used. Thus, the observed yields in the mesophilic DF of FW ranged from 50
359 to 200 NmL H₂/g VS fed, while the reported hydrogen productivities or maximum
360 volumetric hydrogen production rates rarely exceed 1 NL/L-d [34], [35], [36], [37],
361 [38]. For instance, Danko et al. (2008) [39] recorded 154.8 NmL H₂/g VS fed and 100
362 NmL H₂/L-h at a pH of 5.5 using a simulated FW with a formulation similar than that
363 used in the present study. Similarly, Moreno-Andrade et al. (2015) [40] reported a
364 maximum hydrogen productivity of 334.0 ± 56.4 NmL/L-h during the semi-continuous
365 DF of cafeteria FW by a heat shock-pretreated mixed culture at a hydraulic retention
366 time (HRT) of 24 h and 35 °C. Here it is worth noting that the fraction of carbohydrates
367 present in the substrate represents one of the key factors influencing hydrogen
368 production. Alibardi and Cossu (2016) [37] observed a clear correlation between
369 hydrogen production and the percentage of carbohydrates in different FW mixtures,
370 with yields ranging from 189.7 to 229.4 NmL H₂/g carbohydrate fed at a pH of 5.5,
371 which are similar to the 116 and 216 NmL H₂/g carbohydrate recorded in this work
372 (Table 1). It should be noted that hydrogen is mainly produced from lactate rather than
373 from carbohydrates in the LD-DF process, however, carbohydrates are still needed to
374 produce lactate [10]. Overall, the process performance indicators, mainly the
375 outstanding hydrogen productivities (up to ~ 600 NmL/L-h) herein recorded, confirmed
376 the potential advantage of the LD-DF process for FW bioconversion to biohydrogen.

377

378 3.2 pH and TS effect on organic acids production

379 Different organic acids profiles were recorded in the fermentation broth
380 depending on the pH and TS content tested (Fig. 2). In the absence of pH control,
381 neither hydrogen nor CO₂ were produced, but a gradual conversion of the substrate into
382 lactate up to 10.1 ± 1.1 g/L by the end of the process was observed. The production of
383 lactate slowed down throughout the fermentation process, although it continued despite
384 the extremely acid conditions (pH < 4) prevailing during the fermentation. The average
385 acidification degrees (BR) obtained based on the total content of COD in the FW and
386 the corresponding equivalent concentrations of measured organic acids were similar to
387 those estimated on a carbon basis regardless of the condition tested (Table 2). The test
388 performed without pH control exhibited the lowest BR of fermentable substrate to
389 organic acids (~ 16.0), likely due to the reduced acidogenic activity caused by too low
390 pH.

391 At pH 5.5, the kinetics of organic acids production was characterized by an
392 initial stage of lactate accumulation (peaking at 11.5 g/L) and, in a lesser extent, acetate
393 throughout the first 30 h of the process, followed by a stage of lactate and acetate
394 consumption and butyrate production for the next 50–55 hours of fermentation. On the
395 contrary, the kinetics of organic acids production at pH 6.0 and 6.5 were characterized
396 by an initial accumulation and consumption of lactate during the first 24 h,
397 concomitantly with the production of acetate, butyrate and hydrogen. Residual
398 concentrations of isobutyrate (< 0.25 g/L) were also recorded. Lactate accumulation was
399 slightly higher at pH 6.0 compared to pH 6.5, with an average concentration of 3.5 and
400 3.1 g/L, respectively. However, the most favourable pH in terms of BR was 6.5 (Figure
401 2). Interestingly, the cumulative production of hydrogen plateaued with the depletion of

402 lactate, suggesting the occurrence of LD-DF. Metabolically, hydrogen can be produced
 403 not only from carbohydrates but also via lactate-utilizing pathways co-producing
 404 butyrate or acetate [41]. The lactate flux toward acetate could explain the high amounts
 405 of acetate accumulated at pH 6 and 6.5. However, homoacetogenic acetate production
 406 should not be ruled out. According to Eq. 4, the acetate produced by homoacetogenesis
 407 ($A_{\text{Chomoacet}}$) at a fixed TS of 5% accounted for 52.3, 22.5 and 23.6% for pH 5.5, 6.0, and
 408 6.5, respectively. A comparative analysis between the theoretical and real hydrogen
 409 production was conducted considering the concentrations of organic acids measured and
 410 the stoichiometry of hydrogen-producing and hydrogen-utilizing pathways (Eq. 8–11).
 411 Although Eq. 4 overlooks the fate of acetate involved in lactate-utilizing, hydrogen-
 412 producing pathways, the theoretical amounts of hydrogen produced seemed to agree
 413 with that recorded experimentally.

418 On the other hand, low concentrations of formate peaked at 0.1–0.3 g/L but were
 419 further consumed concomitantly with lactate at pH 6.0 and 6.5. The role of formate in
 420 DF remains unclear to date. Its fate can be mediated by microbial lysis into CO_2 and
 421 hydrogen [10], [43]. Interestingly, propionate was gradually produced after lactate
 422 depletion at 24 h of fermentation, reaching a final concentration of 2.4 and 2.1 g/L at pH
 423 6.0 and 6.5, respectively (Fig. 2). Propionate production at neutral pH values has been
 424 reported in the literature [10], [36]. Notably, no propionate accumulation was observed
 425 at pH 5.5, which agrees with previous research [13], [33], [44], [45]. The onset of
 426 propionic-type fermentation is undesirable since it may imply the consumption of

427 hydrogen, which corresponds to the reduction of hydrogen concentration in the
428 acidogenic off-gas observed after lactate depletion. In this context, Cappai et al. (2014)
429 [35] also observed an accumulation of acetate and butyrate within the first hours of
430 fermentation, followed by propionate production when hydrogen production ceased at
431 pH values between 6.0 and 7.0. These authors also observed a residual ethanol
432 production under all conditions tested, which did not occur in the present study (data not
433 shown). This implies that the operational conditions and inoculum herein used
434 prevented the onset of ethanol-type fermentation. In addition, the occurrence of MCCAs
435 was observed only at pH values of 6.0 and 6.5. Caproate and isocaproate were produced
436 at low concentrations (≤ 1.0 g/L) from hour 45 onwards, alongside with residual
437 concentrations of isovalerate.

438 The production kinetics for organic acids at a fixed pH of 6.5 were similar
439 regardless of the TS content tested. The highest acidogenic activity was attained at 7.5%
440 TS (Table 2). However, a lower accumulation of lactate per VS fed (likely mediated by
441 its rapid consumption within the first 24 h of fermentation) was recorded at a TS content
442 of 7.5%, which was approximately 30% lower compared to the assays conducted at a
443 TS content of 5 and 10%. Thus, the highest hydrogen production observed at 7.5% TS
444 was correlated to a lower accumulation (or higher consumption) of lactate. Indeed,
445 hydrogen production ceased when lactate was depleted. In this context, the fact that a
446 superior hydrogen production was positively correlated with a reduced accumulation of
447 lactate, but it ceased with the depletion of lactate, reinforces the hypotheses of the
448 synergistic coupling between lactate producers (LAB) and lactate-utilizing HPB
449 previously outlined in section 3.1. Additionally, higher concentrations of butyrate (8.7
450 g/L), caproate (8.7 g/L), and especially of acetate (10.7 g/L), were accumulated at a TS

451 content of 7.5%, compared to the assays conducted at TS contents of 5% (77.6%, 974%
452 and 26.8%, respectively) and 10% (83.2%, 289% and 62.8%, respectively). Ac_{homoacet}
453 was estimated to be 23.6, 34.9 and 29.6% in the assays conducted at a TS content of 5,
454 7.5 and 10%, respectively. However, as mentioned earlier, it should be taken into
455 account that the lactate flux may be exclusively directed toward acetate or butyrate, both
456 leading to hydrogen production [41]. Finally, the conversion of FW into caproate has
457 been reported to be mediated by lactate-based chain elongation, a pathway that could
458 occur in this study [42]. Overall, the metabolic pathways herein observed strongly
459 suggest the occurrence of LD-DF as the major hydrogen-producing route.

460

461 3.3 Biochemical potential tests

462 The acidogenic effluents obtained at optimal pH and TS content were subjected to BMP
463 tests to elucidate the potential enhancement in the extent and rate of methanization due
464 to the LD-DF process. After 36 days of methanization, the final methane yields from
465 unfermented FW and from 24 and 48 h dark-fermented FW accounted for 346.5, 403.4
466 and 494.7 NmL CH_4/g VS added, respectively (Fig. 3 and Table 3). Therefore, the LD-
467 DF of FW enhanced the extent of methane formation by 16.4 and 42.8% after 24 and 48
468 h of fermentation, respectively. On the other hand, the maximum volumetric methane
469 production rates, R_{max} , were estimated to be 74.2, 68.0 and 92.8 NmL CH_4/h for
470 unfermented FW and from 24 and 48 h dark-fermented FW, respectively. Interestingly,
471 The assay performed with FW fermented for 24 h entailed a decrease in R_{max} by 8.4%
472 compared to the control, while an increase in R_{max} by 25.1% was recorded in the
473 assays with FW fermented for 48 h (Table 3). The *lag* phase of FW biomethanation was
474 not significantly impacted by the LD-DF process, with an increase in λ from 0.9 h for

475 unfermented FW to 1.9 h, regardless of the fermentation period. Finally, the t_{95} in the
476 tests with unfermented FW and 24 and 48 h dark-fermented FW was 13.7, 19.2 and 16.9
477 days, respectively.

478 The difference in composition between the unfermented FW and the fermented
479 FW likely explain the different methane kinetics recorded. On the one hand, the non-
480 fermented FW had a complex but energetically rich composition, composed of
481 polysaccharides, proteins and triglycerides. On the other hand, the fermented substrates
482 were characterized by the presence of high concentrations of organic acids, specifically
483 butyrate and acetate in the case of the FW fermented for 24 h, and caproate, butyrate,
484 isovalerate and isocaproate in the case of FW fermented for 48 h. Although
485 carbohydrates removal was herein not measured, the decrease in VS recorded indicates
486 a significant reduction in organic matter for the dark-fermented FW. Despite the LD-DF
487 process entails an inherent energy loss in the FW due to energy assimilation in the form
488 of biomass, decarboxylation and hydrogen emission, the fermentation process also
489 implies the availability of energy in the form of organic acids, which explains the higher
490 methane yields obtained in the fermented substrates (1.06 g COD of glucose, compared
491 to 1.82 or 2.21 g COD of butyrate or caproate, respectively) [46].

492 The production of methane from raw, unfermented FW was slightly lower
493 compared to the data in literature. Browne and Murphy (2013) [47] compiled data from
494 a large variety of BMP assays and reported yields ranging from 314 to 529 NmL CH₄/g
495 VS added, which were attributed to inoculum acclimation and the use of freshly
496 collected FW. Similarly, Físgativa et al. (2016) [48] obtained an average methane yield
497 of 460.0 ± 87.6 NmL CH₄/g VS added. However, other authors have achieved similar
498 methane yields to those recorded in this work: 364 NmL CH₄/g VS added [49] or 353

499 NmLCH₄/g VS added [50]. On the other hand, most studies reported in literature
500 obtained higher methane yields (on a VS basis) using fermented FW. Thus, Nathao et
501 al. (2013) [51] recorded a yield of 55 NmL H₂/g VS added and 94 NmL CH₄/g VS
502 added in a two-stage FW fermentation, compared to the 82 NmL of CH₄/g VS added
503 obtained in a single stage fermentation. Others, like de Gioannis et al. (2017) [52]
504 reported a yield of 56.5 NmL H₂/g VS added and 392 NmL CH₄/g VS added in a two-
505 stage anaerobic digestion process, compared to the 328.6 NmL CH₄/g VS added in a
506 one stage anaerobic digestion, in an investigation carried out under comparable
507 conditions of pH and FW composition that those used in the present study.

508

509 3.4 Global energy recovery

510 The optimal conditions applied in the LD-DF process of FW for hydrogen production
511 (pH 6.5 and TS 7.5%) supported a net energy recovery yield of 1.32 kJ/g VS fed (Table
512 4). Stoichiometrically, the maximum yield attainable by LD-DF is 4 mol of H₂/mol
513 glucose [33]. Assuming that the main component of FW with hydrogenogenic potential
514 are carbohydrates [37], the yield obtained under optimal conditions was 1.58 mol
515 H₂/mol glucose, followed by 1.24 and 1.22 mol H₂/mol glucose at 5% and 10% TS,
516 respectively, and 1.13 and 0.85 mol H₂/mol_{Glucose} at pH 6.0 and 5.5. This optimal value
517 implied a hydrogen biorecovery efficiency of 40%. In this context, Cappai et al. (2014)
518 [35] obtained H₂ yields varying from 0.31 to 1 mol H₂/mol hexose from different
519 mixtures of FW, where the lowest yields were attributed to the different carbohydrate
520 composition of the FW tested. Similarly, Lee et al. (2014) [36] obtained a yield of 0.88
521 mol H₂/mol hexose at pH 7 and a yield of 1.63 mol H₂/mol hexose at pH 5.3 during the
522 DF of FW.

523 Comparing the experimental energy recovered with the theoretical one (516.2
524 mL CH₄/g VS; 1305.3 kJ) calculated based on Eq. 3 [24], conventional anaerobic
525 digestion of unfermented FW by methanogenesis resulted in an energy recovery ratio of
526 63.6% (824.2 kJ) (Table 5). On the other hand, energy recovery ratios of 48.4% (631.2
527 kJ) and 46.5% (607.1 kJ), accounting for the sum of the H₂ and CH₄ produced (kJ
528 equivalents), were estimated in the FW fermented for 24 and 48 hours, respectively.
529 Interestingly, the H₂ produced from the 24 and 48 h dark-fermented FW represented
530 14.3% (90.4 kJ) and 15.6% (94.5 kJ) of the total energy recovered, which is
531 considerably lower compared to the high VS removal (55.4%) from this DF process.
532 Overall, the LD-DF process resulted in an increase in the methane yield, but it did not
533 offset the losses in VS that occurred during the acidogenic phase.

534

535 **4. Conclusions**

536 The influence of two key process parameters, pH and TS content, on the performance of
537 LD-DF of FW was investigated. The results obtained showed a marked influence of pH
538 and TS content on the hydrogen production performance, leading to a superior hydrogen
539 production when approaching more neutral pH values and increasing the concentration
540 of solids (although a TS content of 10 % became detrimental to the process). The target
541 parameters exerted also a notable effect on the organic acid profile, where a clear
542 correlation was observed between lactate production and consumption, and hydrogen
543 production. A pH of 6.5 and TS of 7.5% was identified as optimal conditions,
544 supporting a hydrogen yield of 103.4 NmL H₂/g VS fed and a maximum volumetric
545 hydrogen production rate of 13.3 NL H₂/L-d, with the concomitant production of 8.7

546 g/L of caproate. Altogether, the LD-DF process shows a high potential for co-producing
547 hydrogen and organic acids including MCCAs from FW.

548

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740 **Figure captions:**

741 **Figure 1.** Time course of the accumulated hydrogen (H₂) produced at different pH
742 values (A) and TS contents (B). The pH tested were 5.5 (■), 6.0 (▲), 6.5 (●) and no pH
743 control (◆). The TS content tested were 5% (●), 7.5% (○) and 10% (△).

744

745 **Figure 2.** Time course of organic acids concentration and hydrogen (H₂) production at
746 A) 5% TS and no pH control; B) 5% TS and pH 5.5; C) 5% TS and pH 6.0; D) 5% TS
747 and pH 6.5; E) 7.5% TS and pH 6.5, and F) 10% TS and pH 6.5.

748

749 **Figure 3.** Time course of methane production for unfermented FW (○) and FW
750 fermented for 24 (●) and 48 (■) hours. Continuous lines indicate the modified Gompertz
751 model prediction.

752 **Table 1.** Hydrogen production yields and Modified Gompertz model kinetic data
 753 obtained in the assays conducted at different pH and TS content.

Condition	H₂/L (NmL)	Yield (NmL H₂/g VS fed)	Yield (NmL H₂/g CH fed)	<i>P</i> (NmL)	<i>Rmax</i> (NmL/h)	λ (h)	R²	
No pH control	0	0	0	0	-	-	-	
pH	5.5	2651	55.4	116	2263	54.0	7.4	0.9954
	6.0	3546	74.1	155.2	2782	163.5	4.5	0.9990
	6.5	3869	80.9	169.4	3080	299.2	6.6	1.0000
TS (%)	7.5	7423	103.4	216.4	5922	444.9	6.3	0.9996
	10%	7643	79.9	166.9	6005	483	6.1	0.9997

754 CH: carbohydrates.

755

756 **Table 2.** Comparison of the COD and carbon equivalents for the different organic acids recorded at the end of the process and associated
 757 bioconversion ratio (BR, acidification degree) for the different pH and TS contents evaluated.

758

Organic acid	COD eq (g COD/L)	BR (% COD)	C eq (g C/g L)	BR (% C)	COD eq (g COD/g L)	BR (% COD)	C eq (g C/g L)	BR (% C)
No pH Control (5% TS)					pH 5.5 (5% TS)			
Lactate	10.7 ± 1.2	15.3 ± 1.7	4.0 ± 0.4	16.1 ± 1.7	0.3 ± .4	0.4 ± 0.6	0.1 ± 0.2	0.4 ± 0.6
Acetate	0.5 ± 0.1	0.7 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.03	0.7 ± 0.1	0.7 ± 0.6	1.0 ± 0.9	0.3 ± 0.2	1.1 ± 1.0
Formate	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1 ± 0.04	0.0	0.1 ± 0.1
Propionate	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Isobutyrate	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1 ± 0.1	0.0	0.1 ± 0.1
Butyrate	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	12.2 ± 0.4	17.4 ± 0.6	3.7 ± 0.1	14.6 ± 0.5
Isovalerate	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Valerate	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Isocaproate	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Caproate	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Total	11.2 ± 1.3	16.0 ± 1.8	4.2 ± 0.5	16.8 ± 1.9	13.3 ± 1.6	19.0 ± 2.3	4.1 ± 0.6	16.4 ± 2.3
pH 6.0 (5% TS)					pH 6.5 (5% TS)			
Lactate	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Acetate	3.0 ± 0.5	4.2 ± 0.7	1.1 ± 0.2	4.4 ± 0.8	6.0 ± 1.0	8.6 ± 1.4	2.3 ± 0.4	9.0 ± 1.5
Formate	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Propionate	3.6 ± 0.5	5.2 ± 0.8	1.2 ± 0.2	4.7 ± 0.7	3.2 ± 1.6	4.5 ± 2.3	1.0 ± 0.5	4.1 ± 2.1
Isobutyrate	0.3 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.2	0.1 ± 0.03	0.4 ± 0.2	0.4 ± 0.1	0.6 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.03	0.5 ± 0.1
Butyrate	3.6 ± 2.1	5.2 ± 3.0	1.1 ± 0.6	4.3 ± 2.5	5.9 ± 0.02	8.4 ± 0.03	1.8 ± 0	7.1 ± 0.03

Isovalerate	0.3 ± 0.4	0.4 ± 0.6	0.1 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.4	0.3 ± 0.4	0.4 ± 0.6	0.1 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.5
Valerate	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Isocaproate	1.1 ± 1.5	1.6 ± 2.2	0.3 ± 0.4	1.2 ± 1.7	0.7 ± 1.0	1.0 ± 1.5	0.2 ± 0.3	0.8 ± 1.1
Caproate	0.4 ± 0.6	0.6 ± 0.8	0.1 ± 0.2	0.5 ± 0.7	1.2 ± 1.7	1.7 ± 2.4	0.3 ± 0.5	1.4 ± 1.9
Total	12.3 ± 5.8	17.6 ± 8.3	4.0 ± 1.8	15.9 ± 7.1	17.7 ± 5.9	25.4 ± 8.4	5.8 ± 1.8	23.2 ± 7.3
	7.5% TS (pH 6.5)				10% TS (pH 6.5)			
Lactate	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Acetate	11.4 ± 1.5	10.8 ± 1.4	4.3 ± 0.6	11.4 ± 1.5	9.3 ± 1.5	6.7 ± 1.1	3.5 ± 0.6	7.0 ± 1.1
Formate	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Propionate	6.5 ± 0.7	6.2 ± 0.7	2.1 ± 0.2	5.6 ± 0.6	5.4 ± 1.5	3.9 ± 1.1	1.7 ± 0.5	3.5 ± 1.0
Isobutyrate	1.1 ± 0.1	0.8 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.03	0.8 ± 0.1	0.5	0.4	0.1	0.3
Butyrate	15.7 ± 2.1	15.0 ± 2.1	4.7 ± 0.7	12.6 ± 1.7	11.5 ± 2.8	8.2 ± 2.0	3.5 ± 0.8	6.9 ± 1.7
Isovalerate	1.0 ± 1.4	1.0 ± 1.4	0.3 ± 0.4	0.8 ± 1.1	0.9	0.7	0.3	0.5
Valerate	1.8 ± 1.8	1.8 ± 1.8	0.5 ± 0.5	1.4 ± 1.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Isocaproate	2.4 ± 0.7	2.3 ± 0.7	0.7 ± 0.2	1.8 ± 0.5	1.7 ± 0.7	1.2 ± 0.5	0.5 ± 0.2	1.0 ± 0.4
Caproate	19.2 ± 0.2	18.3 ± 0.2	5.4 ± 0.06	14.4 ± 0.2	6.6 ± 0.6	4.7 ± 0.5	1.8 ± 0.2	3.7 ± 0.4
Total	59.1 ± 5.4	56.1 ± 5.2	18.3 ± 1.8	48.8 ± 4.8	36.0 ± 7.2	25.7 ± 5.1	11.5 ± 2.3	22.9 ± 4.6

759 **Table 3.** Modified Gompertz kinetic model data obtained from the BMP assays with
 760 non-fermented FW (NFFW) and dark-fermented FW for 24 (F24) and 48 (F48) hours.

	<i>P</i> (mL/g VS fed)	<i>Rmax</i> (mL/L-day)	λ (days)	R²
NFFW	325.9	74.2	0.9	0.997
F24	403.7	68	1.9	0.999
F48	477.8	92.8	1.9	0.998

761

762 **Table 4.** Energy recovery in the FW fermentation for H₂ production carried out at
 763 different pH and TS contents.

Condition		H₂ yield (mol H₂/mol glucose)	Energy yield (kJ/g VS fed)	Energy produced (kJ)	Recovery (%)
pH	uncontrolled pH	0	0	0	0
	5.5	0.85	0.71	33.53	21
	6.0	1.13	0.94	44.85	28
	6.5	1.24	1.03	48.96	31
TS (%)	7.5 % TS	1.58	1.32	94.87	40
	10% TS	1.22	1.02	97.17	31

764 *Recovery* indicates the percentage of H₂ produced compared to the theoretical
 765 maximum.
 766
 767

768 **Table 5.** Energy recovery data from raw and fermented FW.

	CH₄ yield (NmL/g VS fed)	Energy yield (kJ/g VS fed)	VS fed (g/L)	Total energy produced (kJ)	Recovery (%)
Unfermented FW	346.5	12.17	72	876.2	67.1
24h	403.4	14.17	38.2	631.9	48.4
48h	494.7	17.37	29.5	607.1	46.51

769 *Total Energy Produced* indicates the total energy recovered from the LD-DF +
770 methanogenic process. *Recovery* indicates the percentage of energy recovered (H₂ +
771 CH₄) compared to the theoretical maximum (%), based on Eq. 3.

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773

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Fig. 1

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Fig. 2

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Fig. 3